

Exploring the Effectiveness of Gratitude Journaling in Enhancing Mental Health among College Students

Roshni Singh¹ and Sonam Kumari Rawat²

*Department of Psychology, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh¹
Department of Psychology, Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareli, (Associated with University of Lucknow, Lucknow) Uttar Pradesh²*

College students are the most vulnerable population to mental health issues due to academic stress, career pressure, and social challenges during the transition into adulthood, as well as into college life. These stressors often lead to reduce Mental Health, increased anxiety and burnout. This research aims to enhance the Mental Health of college students with the help of Gratitude Journaling. The study recruited 29 college students through purposive sampling. Gratitude journaling, a positive psychology practice that involves regularly noting things one is thankful for, has shown promise in enhancing emotional resilience and fostering positive mental states. The study assessed students' level of Mental Health before and after journaling using the World Health Organization-Five Well-Being Index (WHO-5). To meet the research objective, data will be analysed using descriptive statistics and a paired t-test. Results indicate that there is no significant difference between before and after gratitude journaling. The study would contribute to empirical evidence on the role of Gratitude Journaling in improving students' Mental Health, and also provide practical implications for designing low-cost, scalable Mental Health programs in higher education institutions and workplace.

Keywords: Gratitude Journaling, mental health, and college students

Mental health is a state of well-being that focuses on the development of a fully functioning person in the absence of disease and on identifying their own potential to contribute effectively towards the community (WHO, 2001; MHF, 2008; Bhugra et al., 2013). Mental health problems can be prevalent in any age group, but they are common and easily observed among college students as they are the most vulnerable population to mental health issues due to academic stress, career pressure, and social challenges (Pedrelli, et al., 2015; Balon et al., 2015). Anxiety, Depression, high levels of stress and academic pressure are the most prevalent mental health challenges that can be found in the population of college students

Kang et al. (2021) and Pedrelli et al. (2015). The major cause of social pressure among them (Spytska, 2023) needs an effective and accessible support mechanism. Suffering from any type of mental health issue adversely affects education (Kondirolli, 2022). Maintaining the mental health and psychological stability of students and young people is extremely important, as they are the backbone of a nation's development. Identifying effective early intervention strategies is crucial for developing long-term effects on students' well-being.

One of the effective and newly emerging therapeutic fields is

Author Note

¹Roshni Singh, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

²Dr. Sonam Kumari Rawat, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareli, (Associated with University of Lucknow, Lucknow), Uttar Pradesh

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to

Roshni Singh, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology

University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

E-mail: singhsaumya030@gmail.com

positive psychotherapy, which includes a variety of interventions focused on strengthening positive emotions. Positive psychotherapy under the influence of a professional therapist and counsellor is seen as beneficial to reduce anxiety (Hyadri et al., 2018). There is a spectrum of positive psychology interventions, among them mindfulness is most effective in managing emotions and enhancing mental health (Melnyk et al., 2020). Mindfulness is a technique used to make individuals aware of their own cognition (Germer, 2004). Mindfulness can be practiced in various ways including meditation, writing affirmations, etc. (Priebe et al., 2022; Dundas & Nygard, 2024; Lothas, 2025). One of the effective interventions to maintain and enhance the level of mental health is gratitude journaling, a positive psychology intervention influenced by expressive writing. Gratitude journaling provides a platform to acknowledge and appreciate the positive aspects of life (Kaur et al., 2025). Gratitude journaling focuses on reflecting on positive thoughts via writing and creating new and positive meaning to one's daily experience (Tan et al., 2021). It focuses on inter as well as intra-personal processes of journaling. The intrapersonal process of gratitude journaling stimulates the positive emotion within the individual, while the interpersonal process helps to recognise the positive impacts of others (Işık & Tekinalp, 2017). Among all the other interventions, gratitude journaling has appeared as the most effective intervention for improving well-being and affective functioning (Tolcher et al., 2024). Gratitude has shown its positive effect on sleep improvement, anxiety, stress, self-esteem, etc., with a fostered positive sense of overall well-being (Tan et al., 2021).

Roche et al. (2023) conducted a study on health care workers to analyse the effect of gratitude journaling and cognitive strategies. The study reported no difference between the effects of the strategies used. However, the effect of the gratitude journaling on depression and anxiety was not significant, but participants reported it as worthwhile and helpful. Another research tries to explore the effect

of mindfulness and gratitude journaling to reduce exam anxiety, reporting the combined intervention as an effective technique to reduce anxiety (Jain, 2020) and improve students' overall well-being by implying strength management technique with gratitude journaling (Flinchbaugh et al., 2011). Studies have suggested that combined interventions sometimes help in the improvement of overall well-being and mental health; however, a few studies also reported non-significant yet positive changes.

Gratitude Journaling, as an independent intervention, has also shown a notable impact in improving the overall well-being of college students (James et al., 2023). A study conducted by Lima (2025) reported that gratitude journaling shown effect in enhancing emotional well-being by enhancing positive emotion while reducing depression and anxiety. It also indicates that gratitude journaling can be an effective psychoeducational strategy for reducing academic stress and promoting emotional well-being (Layyinah et al., 2026). Another study tries to explore the effectiveness of mindfulness-based intervention with the help of guided intervention; the 14-day study shows substantial improvement in subjective happiness (Devassykutty & Jose, 2025). Fernando (2026) adopted gratitude journaling to enhance mental well-being. The research adopted two methods to check the mental well-being: one via text and another via visualized gratitude journaling. The study reported that the visualized gratitude journaling was more effective and sustainable than the text-based gratitude journaling.

Literature indicates journaling as an intervention that involves several complexities, including varying types of journals, their content, duration, frequency, as well as the way to guide journaling, all of which can directly influence the effectiveness of the process (Sohal et al., 2022). There are several studies available for mixed types of intervention to analyse the individual overall well-being, and gratitude journaling as an independent intervention among college students in this era is limited. Thus, the current study focused on examining the effectiveness of gratitude journaling on enhancing mental health among college students.

Method

Participants

The study employed purposive sampling, with the inclusion criteria of 18 to 25 years college students enrolled in any type of course on a full-time basis. The sample consists of 29 individuals, where 48.3% participant were female and 51.7% were male. The mean age range is 21.48 for the age range of 18-25 years. All the participants belong to the same ethnic group of Asian People and of the same nationality, Indian.

Research Design

To understand the effectiveness of gratitude journaling among college students, a quasi-experimental study with a one-group pre-test and post-test design has been adopted. With the help of this design, the data have been collected before and after the intervention with standardized questionnaires.

Measures

Demographic Questionnaire: Participants' names, Age, and Gender have been collected with the help of the Demographic Questionnaire. *The World Health Organization- Five Well-Being Index (WHO-5):* The WHO-5 scale was developed by de Graaff and van Ommeren

(Mental Health Unit, Department of Mental Health, Brain Health & Substance Use, WHO) in 2024. The test consists of 5 statements to measure an individual's mental health and well-being. Each item is marked from the range of 0 to 5. The raw scores were obtained from 0 to 25 points. 0 representing the worst possible mental well-being and 25 representing the best possible mental well-being. The Cronbach alpha reliability of the instrument is 0.79.

Procedure

This study was conducted on individuals aged between 18-25 years, from both urban and rural areas. The study included 30 participants earlier, but one participant was removed due to an incomplete form, leading to 29 participants in the final study. The participants were briefed about the gratitude journaling, its nature, its benefits, and its effectiveness in improving overall well-being. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants. The pre-test was administered with the help of the WHO-5 questionnaire of well-being. After data collection for the pre-test, each participant was provided with the basic instructions on how to do gratitude journaling. The instructions regarding gratitude journaling were as follows:

- Think of five positive events from the day (it could be a big achievement or small, enjoyable moments).
- Write each event in a diary.
- For each event, read it, then close your eyes and recall the event.
- Write down the emotions or feelings associated with it below the corresponding point.

Participants were told to do the gratitude journaling at the end of the day for 15 days continuously. After the desired time period of 15 days, a post-test was conducted with the help of the same questionnaire.

Results

The measures were scored in accordance with the response guidelines. To analyse the effectiveness of gratitude journaling in enhancing mental health, a pre and post-test study has been conducted and a paired t-test was used to compare means between pre and post-test scores. The computation of descriptive statistics, concerning the demographic variables, is displayed in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. There are (N=29) in the sample with a minimum age of 18 and a maximum age of 25 years. The 51.7% were males, while females were 48.3%. Table 2 indicates the descriptive statistics, which shows the mean score of mental health on the WHO-5 scale before gratitude journaling was 15.26 with SD= 4.87. After the intervention, the mean score of mental health was 16.24 with SD= 5.62. The mean increased by 0.586 indicating the improved level of mental health after gratitude journaling.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Demographic variable	Number & percentage	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Age	29	21.48	1.84	0.24	-0.56
Gender		1.48	.509	0.073	-2.14
Male	51.7%				
Female	48.3%				

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of Pre-test and Post-test

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pre Test	29	15.65	4.87
Post Test	29	16.24	5.62

Table 3

Test of Normality

	Shapiro-Wilk Statistic		
		df	Sig
Pretest	.963	29	.379
Post-test	.947	29	.150

In Table 3, the test of Normality was also performed to select the appropriate method for inferential statistical analysis. The Shapiro-Wilk test was applied for normality as the sample size of the study is less than 50. The level of significance for pre and post -test were 0.379 and 0.150, respectively. The level of significance for the dependent variable was normally distributed (>0.05) for both pre and post- test. Along with the test of normality, a QQ plot has also been

generated to assess the normality of the data. In Figure 1, it can be seen that the data is normally distributed as the data points are clustered around the diagonal line.

Figure 1

Q-Q Plot

Table 4

Paired Sample Tests

	Paired Differences							
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std Error Mean	95 % Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper			
	Pretest-Post-test	-0.586	4.136	0.768	-2.159	0.987	-0.763	28

Since normality was demonstrated, parametric testing was used to perform inferential analysis of the scores. Paired-Sample t-test was used to compare the mean scores of mental health on the WHO-5 Scale before and after the intervention of gratitude journaling. Table 4 indicates that there was no significant increase in mental health scores before gratitude journaling ($M = 15.66, SD = 4.87$) and after gratitude journaling ($M = 16.24, SD = 5.62$), $t(29) = -0.76, p = 0.452$ (two-tailed). The mean increase in score was 0.586 with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -0.215 to 0.987.

Discussion

Being a college student comes with a lot of mental pressure and challenges. The constant expectation for academic excellence induces negative feelings and thoughts about oneself. In order to address these challenges number of interventions could be applied such as mindfulness, cognitive and behavioural strategies (Roche et al., 2023; Jain, 2020). One of the effective techniques that could be used to enhance the mental health of college students is Gratitude journaling. The present study aimed to explore the effectiveness of gratitude journaling in enhancing the mental health of college students. In contrast with the previous effective nature of gratitude journaling (Lima, 2025; Layyinah et al., 2026; Devassykutty & Jose, 2025; Fernando, 2026), the current study revealed that gratitude journaling is not significantly effective to enhance the mental health of college students, the results still show some positive changes

within the participants. There are several studies which shows that gratitude journaling combined with different interventions shows a positive effect on the individual's overall well-being (Flinchbaugh et al., 2011; Jain, 2020).

The present findings can be supported by evidence drawn from studies exploring the effect of gratitude journaling in the various spectrum of anxiety and well-being among different populations.

Roche et al. (2023) conducted a study to assess impact of gratitude journaling on mental health of paediatric health care workers (HCWs) including nurses and physicians. They were provided with training on gratitude journaling in a 15 min zoom-session and a guided gratitude journal. The study was conducted for a short-period of time. The HCWs were asked to do the journaling at the start and end of the day for 2 weeks. The results of study were non-significant for decreasing depression and anxiety among the HCWs. A similar study was conducted by Sutschet (2025) and Louise Adler (2025) to examine the effect of gratitude journaling on depressive symptoms and anxiety levels among students and young professionals. However, the findings indicated no effect of gratitude journaling on reducing depressive symptoms among this population.

Sadia, Perveen, and Iqbal (2023) argued that gratitude has a weak association with anxiety. Students can show gratitude, yet shows the signs of anxiety. Any token of positive words can be useful in motivating the students but it does not prove to be helpful in reducing the exam anxiety symptoms among students.

Based on the cognitive theoretical work by Eysenck and Clavo (1992) individuals experiencing stress and anxiety are more likely to generate negative thoughts that are unrelated to the task at hand. Consequently, their available cognitive resources are exhausted, as the major portion of their attention is occupied by worry and negative thoughts. Based on this perspective, daily journaling may be perceived as a burden because it demands additional mental effort.

A gratitude journal involves recording any aspect of life for which an individual is thankful. However, several factors must be considered to ensure the effectiveness of gratitude journaling, such as training participants on how to practice gratitude journaling effectively (Sohal et al., 2022)

The gratitude journal refers to keeping an account in written form of things that an individual is thankful for and the positive events he/she notices in everyday life. However, there are certain variables that are required to be taken into account to design the gratitude journal as an efficient intervention. (Sohal et al., 2022). A detailed training on how to effectively do gratitude journaling and to make participants understand how gratitude journaling works is required. The lack of training sessions reduces the effect of gratitude journaling (Sohal et al., 2022).

Although the difference between pre-test and post-test scores indicates a positive change, the effect was not strong enough to confirm the effectiveness of the intervention. One of the possible explanations is that the current study doesn't imply training the participants about journaling without considering it as another stressful cognitive work, and the inability to check on the progress of gratitude journaling and guiding them could be another possible reason for non-significant result. Therefore, future research should consider implementing guided gratitude journaling along with training sessions to help participants understand the purpose, process and techniques involved. Providing such detailed guidance may enhance engagement of the participants and may help researchers to accurately evaluate the effectiveness of intervention.

Conclusion

The current study aimed to explore the effectiveness of gratitude journaling in enhancing mental health among college students. The finding revealed that the difference between the level of mental health in pre and post-test was not statistically significant, but a moderate level of difference was observed. Thus, it warrants more intense and longitudinal research on the topic, along with the structured and guided type of gratitude journaling.

Future and Implications of the Study

The result of the study provides insight to promote emotional awareness and self-reflection among college students. It also suggests developing students' wellness programs and providing counselling services to deal with their mental stressors effectively. The study also points towards the development of a low-cost, useful, and self-help mental health tool to assess and manage mental health. This research also highlights the need to support research on positive psychology interventions.

Limitations and Suggestions

This study has several limitations despite its significant contribution. The sample size of the study is relatively small, and the interventions have only been applied for 15 days without any guided way of

journaling. The response biases might be another limitation of the study as being too much on self-reported data. Future studies should try to focus on a large and diverse sample with an extended period of intervention. Future studies can also include a control group for a better comparison. They can also provide the guided journaling instructions in the hope of better results.

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